

Advancing Resilience of the Built Environment by Digital and Measurement Technologies

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Abstract— *The built environment faces increasing pressure from climate change and natural hazards like heatwaves, floods, earthquakes, and droughts. Dedicating resources to resilience is the key to safeguarding communities and investments, paving the way to an ecosystem able to effectively face emergencies linked to natural hazards. The MULTICLIMACT European project offers innovative technical and digital solutions across three scales: buildings, urban, and territorial. Through the development of design practices, materials and technologies, and digital solutions, the project bolsters construction resilience, preparedness, and responsiveness to disruptive events, improving safety and quality of living. Innovative sensing technologies are considered to continuously monitor the whole ecosystem, supporting management strategies and ensuring timely interventions when needed. At the building scale, the project crafts tools and methodologies to evaluate and enhance the resilience of existing and new constructions. At the urban scale, emphasis is placed on sustainable planning strategies and land management, incorporating measures such as green infrastructure and stormwater management to boost resilience against extreme weather conditions. At the territorial scale, the project integrates climate adaptation policies and territorial planning. All the design procedures are human centred in order to foster well-being and health conditions in the living environments. MULTICLIMACT raises a resilience culture and deploys innovative and nature-based solutions to ensure safety and sustainability, taking advantages and exploiting the synergies of a multidisciplinary consortium involving enterprises and research entities from many European countries.*

Keywords— *Built Environment; Resilience; Natural Hazards; Climate Adaptation; Technical and Digital Solutions; Measurements.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The built environment is essential for the functioning of our modern society and economy, by providing the fundamental physical and organizational structures and facilities that underpin many of our activities. Indeed, it is strictly related to human behaviour as well as to structures and infrastructures [1]. Urban planning should be based on the relationships between built environment and its occupants' well-being, considering the different destinations of use that a building can cover [2]. On the other hand, even though most

infrastructure assets have a long lifespan or service life, many of those currently within the EU were designed and built decades ago. According to Gevorgian et al. [3], 31% of the residential European building stock was built before 1945 and only 12% belongs to the post-2010 epoch. Renovation actions are pivotal to enhance the energy efficiency of building stock as well as make it resilient and durable according to the present conditions. To this end, the European Union has released many documents, packages, and initiatives like Renovation Wave [4] and Fit for 55 [5]. In this situation, climate change continues to increase the frequency and the severity of a range of climate and weather extremes, significantly impacting their functionality [6] as well as the entire built environment across multiple levels [7]. This condition emphasizes and underscores the urgent necessity of transitioning towards a climate-resilient society, by building up our adaptive capacity and minimizing our vulnerability; European initiatives, such as “Forging a climate-resilient Europe” [8], underline the importance to find smart, systematic, and swift solutions to respond to extreme weather events. Not considering climate change related aspects when renovating buildings can result in significant underestimations of costs and environmental impacts [9]. What is more, actions targeting an increasing of resilience should walk hand in hand with sustainable solutions, aiming at achieving smart cities capable to optimize quality of life as well as use resources responsibly. Just as an example, Taherkhani et al. [10] proposed a framework prioritizing factors dealing with sustainability and resilience for renovating a historic district; they underlined the relevance of raising the citizens' awareness on these topics, which is pivotal in a society preferring to renovate buildings in the city than moving outside. Strategies for a risk-informed sustainable development should become common for decision-makers [11]; resilience has become a design problem and renovation approaches should aim at extending service life considering at the same time durability and adaptability [12]. Also the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) defined by the United Nations [13] target the resilience of the built environment, aiming at resilient, safe, and sustainable communities. In particular, the SDG n. 9 aims to build resilient

and sustainable infrastructures, sustaining human well-being. The SDG n. 11 promotes sustainable cities and communities, highlighting themes as safety, durability, and inclusive urbanization; vulnerability is considered in relation to natural hazards, and efforts are made to find mitigation and adaptation strategies for climate change. The importance of these themes is clear; the citizens' preparedness to face also the most catastrophic events should be fostered and this objective requires a great effort to raise their awareness and do significant steps towards resilient smart cities. It is worthy to underline the importance of renovating actions also with a view of improving the citizens' quality of life and well-being; the use of different and complementary technologies, materials, and skills is fundamental, since a multidisciplinary approach is pivotal to achieve these ambitious aims [14]. Digital and sensing technologies and early warning systems are just a few examples in this field [15,16]. Building Information Modelling (BIM) and Digital Twin can for sure contribute to a smoother management of buildings [17,18], easing the accessibility of structures and infrastructures information also in real-time; moreover, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms can play a key role in data analysis [19,20], providing indicators and forecasting that can pave the way to new means of managing smart cities.

In this context, the MULTICLIMACT project [21] aims to enhance the resilience of the built environment against climate-related threats, by establishing a framework for assessing resilience at various scales (buildings, urban areas, territories), improving preparedness and providing practical and cost-effective methods to enhance resilience, incorporating a multidisciplinary approach and taking advantage of synergistic competences. The sought solutions include sensing and digital technologies as well as innovative sustainable materials and solutions, hence considering the objective to be reached with a holistic approach.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows: Section II contextualize the project and describes its objectives; Section III details the project demo cases; Section IV shows the technical, sensing, and digital solutions employed in the project with the common aim to enhance the resilience of the built environment. Finally, the Authors provide their final remarks in Section V.

II. CONTEXT AND GENERAL OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The general context where MULTICLIMACT is attempt to develop and provide efficient solutions with high scientific value to society is dominated by global risks, including the failure to mitigate the severity of climate change, risks related to natural disasters and extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem collapse [22]. The three pillars on which the MULTICLIMACT project is centered are vulnerability, adaptation, and resilience (Fig. 1). Vulnerability focuses on the ability to resist and mitigate damage from risks, aiming to improve safety with force as the controlling parameter. On the other hand, adaptation involves adjusting to current or anticipated climate changes through actions (like building protective structures, improving systems, and choosing crops wisely). The goal of adaptation is to minimize harm while also seizing opportunities for sustainability and resilience.

Within the project, resilience is perceived as the ability to adapt, absorb, and recover from risks by involving development plans, strategies, and resources for adaptation and recovery with time as a controlling parameter. Climate vulnerability and risk assessments contribute to the

Fig. 1 Pillars of the MULTICLIMACT project.

identification of significant climate risks and serve as the basis for identifying, appraising, and implementing targeted adaptation measures. This process aims to reduce residual risk to an acceptable level under the umbrella of a holistic resilient approach, involving both the built environment and dwellers, addressing specific local needs and potentials.

The MULTICLIMACT objectives are divided into Scientific/Technological Objectives (STO) and Non-Technological ones (NTO), as the dissemination and the awareness of such research initiatives demands also the enabling of social factors and society in order to be translated into tangible results. The STO are listed below:

- STO1: Setting up a mainstreamed framework for assessing the resilience of the built environment against locally relevant climatic and natural hazards and supporting public decision-makers to evaluate and implement resilience-enabling interventions across the whole life cycle.
- STO2: Development of design practices and methods on the built environment supporting and enhancing its resilience to natural hazards.
- STO3: Development of materials and technologies for supporting the built environment preparedness and responsiveness to disrupting events.
- STO4: Development of digital solutions aimed at enhancing monitoring, detecting, and responding to critical situations.
- STO5: Demonstration of the MULTICLIMACT framework in four climatic and social contexts, as well as considering different locally relevant hazards and scales.

These goals reflect the willingness and the determination not only to provide stand-alone advanced solutions for specific problems, but also to include them into a holistic resilient framework that aligns with established design, policy practices and methods. Furthermore, the intention is to demonstrate these solutions through exemplary cases.

The NTO express the goal of raising awareness of the human factor, and they are presented below:

- NTO1: Delivering an early, open, and transparent strategy for the promotion of MULTICLIMACT framework and results through a comprehensive Dissemination and Communication plan.
- NTO2: Deploying a sound strategy towards the exploitation and market uptake of MULTICLIMACT

results, including social innovation practices and innovative business models.

- NTO3: Implementing ambitious international outreach, communication, and cooperation activities for replicating and scaling up the MULTICLIMACT framework.

III. TECHNOLOGICAL, SENSING, AND DIGITAL SOLUTIONS

Within the framework of the MULTICLIMACT project, a plethora of innovative technological, sensing, and digital solutions are put in place in order to achieve synergistic results taking benefit from the multidisciplinary consortium involved in the project, including 26 partners (industries, universities, and research centres) from 9 different European countries.

Measurement and monitoring solutions will play a particularly relevant role, providing data at different levels to guarantee a proper picture of the entire context and, hence, support the management of living environments at different scales. The solutions are tailored according to the needs of different environments, considering territorial and cultural peculiarities as well as the hazards affecting each area. Different types of events will be accounted for, such as earthquakes, heat waves, draughts, floods, and weather-induced landslides. Innovative materials enhancing self-sensing capabilities (e.g., thanks to the addition of sustainable carbon-based materials as biochar and carbon fibres) and improving the occupants' well-being (e.g., multifunctional mortar improving indoor air quality) will be exploited as well as solutions to improve energy efficiency (e.g., advanced HVAC systems). Digital solutions (e.g., development and exploitation of BIM and Digital Twins integrated in holistic monitoring platforms) will be tailored to the specific needs of the different applications in the view of a digital transition fostering the renovation of the European building stock and measurement solutions will be in strict relation to them. The informative content of the measured data will be fully exploited and integrated into the BIM of the various use cases, incorporating the occupants' data from a human-centric perspective. In this way, both buildings performance and human well-being can be enhanced and the information can be exploited for management purposes as well as decision-making processes.

Moreover, the design of these solutions is always oriented to the real users' needs, in order to tailor tools and technologies at best and effectively support the entire society who has to tackle certain risks. In this context, particular attention is paid to well-being, as it is well-known that it directly influences several human spheres, like productivity and health.

The main outputs of the MULTICLIMACT project, derived from the application of the consortium's multidisciplinary competences along with the addressed risks for each demonstrator, are reported in Table I.

IV. DEMONSTRATION CASES

The outcomes of the developed MULTICLIMACT solutions will be tested to prove their beneficial contribution to the project goals. There will be 5 demonstration cases, covering a wide range of European territory types, from Mediterranean to the Baltic Sea. The demonstration cases, along with the foreseen technologies, are described below:

- Italian Demo: Fazzini student residence (Fig. 2)

The demo is located in Camerino, in the Marche region, in a hilly landscape typical of the Umbria-Marche Apennines. The

Fig. 3 City centre (top) and Superilles (bottom) (Barcelona, Spain – Spanish demo site).

Fig. 2 Fazzini student residence (Camerino, Italy – Italian demo site).

area is characterized by a high seismic risk and Mediterranean climate conditions. Therefore, the addressed natural and climatic hazards would include heat waves and earthquakes. The foreseen intervention includes a seismic protection system with innovative components (energy dissipation trough viscous dampers and external fixed braces) and an energetic retrofitting of building envelopes and plant systems. The implementation of climate-proofing measures will range at different scales and a monitoring system will be deployed to support timely interventions through a dedicated early warning system.

- Spanish Demo: Barcelona city centre (Fig. 3)

The demo is located in Barcelona, where, similarly to the previous case, Mediterranean climate conditions are present. The natural and climatic hazards addressed would include urban heat waves and floodings. The foreseen intervention includes the implementation of energy retrofit strategies for climate-proofing and the development of recycled pavements along with nature-based solutions and advanced water management techniques. There will be also a characterization of thermal and energy solutions at the district level as part of the digital solutions portfolio.

- Dutch demo n. 1: Tedingerbroekpolder dike (Fig. 4)

The dike is located in the city of Hague, serving as an inner protective flood defence for the Tedingerbroek polder. The dike is part of an ancient polder area between Zoetermeer, Leidschendam, Voorburg, Hague and Nootdorp. The climate conditions refer to those of Western Europe. The addressed

Fig. 4 Tedingerbroekpolder dike (polder area between Zoetermeer, Leidschendam, Voorburg, Hague and Nootdorp, Netherlands – Dutch demo site n. 1).

natural and climatic hazards would consist of extreme temperatures (both low and high), heavy precipitation, flooding, drought, and heatwaves. The planned interventions include monitoring of temperature and acoustics using Fiber-Optics sensors for measuring moisture content and vibrations (primarily related to cracking), implementing resilience-enabling interventions in cultural heritage buildings and urban/rural areas. and developing and testing of an early warning monitoring system for flood defence systems during flood and drought events.

- Dutch demo n. 2: Limburgse Roermond Tributary (Groen Riveir) (Fig. 5)

The Groen Rivier is located between the Hambeek and the Roer rivers, and it was constructed in the early 1990s as a last resort to relieve the Hambeek during high water. The climate conditions refer again to those of Western Europe. The addressed natural and climatic hazards would be heavy precipitation and flooding. The foreseen intervention includes the monitoring of strain and temperature of movable barriers in place during operation of the diversion gate for crisis management, implementing resilience-enabling interventions in cultural heritage buildings and urban/rural areas, and developing and testing of an early warning monitoring system for flood defence systems during flood and drought events.

- Latvian demo: Riga Central Market (Fig. 6)

The demo is located in Riga Old Town, which is considered a UNESCO World Heritage Site, in a coastal urban area particularly vulnerable to flood risks, storm surges and flash floods. The climate conditions refer again to those of Northern Europe. The addressed natural and climatic hazards would include extreme temperatures (both low and high), heat islands in urban environments, heavy precipitation, flooding, drought, earthquakes, and heatwaves. The foreseen intervention includes implementing a passive-low temperature heating and passive cooling system to adapt the cultural heritage buildings to the effects of global warming as well as enhancing resilience for the built environment by incorporating supply chain considerations and life-cycle analysis in cultural heritage and urban contexts. Furthermore, the implementation of climate-proofing energy planning solutions is also being considered.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the current article, the authors have briefly described the broader landscape of the impact and the imposed threats to the built environment due to climate change. MULTICLIMACT general objectives and the pillars on which the project will base in order to achieve and exceed its expectations were presented too. The exploited technologies have been listed

Fig. 5 Limburgse Roermond Tributary (Netherlands – Dutch demo site n. 2).

Fig. 6. Central marker (Riga, Latvia – Latvian demo site).

together with their potentialities. Finally, an overview of the exemplary demonstration cases, in which the foreseen design, material and digital solutions will be tested, has been provided.

The solutions developed within the framework of MULTICLIMACT target the society as a whole, contributing to the human-centred climate resilience of the built environment. This can reduce costs from climate related damages and improve energy efficiency, also thanks to the innovative sensing and digital solutions. Furthermore, sustainable materials contribute to lower the environmental impact of the built environment.

Communication and dissemination activities of the project will be regularly performed for all the project duration to maximise the impact of the achieved results, hoping that the proposed approach could be scaled and adapted also to different application contexts.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research activity was carried out within the MULTICLIMACT (MULTI-faceted CLIMate adaptation ACTIONS to improve resilience, preparedness and responsiveness of the built environment against multiple hazards at multiple scales) project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101123538.

TABLE I. DEMO SITES: TECHNOLOGIES EMPLOYED AND RISKS ADDRESSED.

Demo	Risks addressed					Employed technologies		
	Eartquakes	Flooding	Drought	Heat waves	Heat island effect	Materials	Sensing/monitoring technologies	Digital technologies
Italian	x	x	-	x	-	Self-sensing materials, multifunctional mortar improving air quality. Materials for renovation.	Sensors for environmental, physiological, and SHM parameters.	BIM-based digital platform; app for early warnings; information to support decision-making.
Spanish	-	x	-	x	x	Sustainable materials from circular supply-chains.	Measurement of thermal and energy parameters.	Data-driven solutions.
Dutch	-	x	x	-	-	-	Fiber-optics based sensors.	Early warning solutions.
Latvian	-	x	x	x	x	Circular supply chains.	Heating and cooling systems.	Energy-planning solutions.

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